

Survey: Needs & gaps within and across regions and the
associated local contexts

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TABLE 1: PARTICIPANTS

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Document summary

A stakeholder survey was completed within each project country to identify the needs and barriers for alternative weed control uptake. In this context, needs are defined as actions required to increase uptake of alternative weed control. Barriers are defined as the socio-economic, political, regulatory, biophysical and technological gaps that may prevent farmers from increasing their uptake of alternative weed control solutions.

Online survey questions; needs & barriers for alternative weed control.

2. Which country do you live in?

- France
- Greece
- Italy Latvia
- Spain
- Sweden
- UK
- Other

2.a. If you selected Other, please specify:

3. Do you see yourself as a farmer or non-farmer?

- Farmer Non-
- farmer

4. How many ha of agricultural land do you manage/own?

- up to 5ha
- 5.1 to 10ha
- 10.1 to 30ha
- 30.1 to 100ha
- 100.1 to 300ha
- 300.1 - 500ha
- 500.1 - 1000ha
- over 1000ha

5. Which is the predominant crop type on your farm (please tick one option)?

If you manage several crops, please indicate the type providing the highest revenue.

- 1) Cereals/oilseeds
- 2) Potatoes and sugar beet
- 3) Vegetables
- 4) Vineyards
- 5) Other fruit
- 6) Other crops

5.a. If you selected 'other crops', please type your answer below.

6. How would you describe your weed management?

Note: Here, 'chemical' does not refer to the usage of bio-herbicides

- 1) Organic (no chemical inputs)
- 2) Integrated pest/weed management (IPM/IWM)
- 3) Conventional (reliant on chemical herbicides)

- 4) Conservation agriculture
- 5) Regenerative agriculture
- 6) Agroecological
- 7) Other

6.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

Current weed control problems / farmers

7. Which weed control methods are you currently using (multiple options possible)? Please indicate methods that you are using and select or specify one main disadvantage (if any) of the approach.

	Select	Main disadvantage	If you selected 'other', please specify in the box
herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mechanical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
camera guided inter- row or intra- row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultivations	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultural control (delayed drilling, rotations, cover crops, cultivar choice, high seed rates)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mowing	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
weeding by hand	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mulches (membranes, organic)/living mulches	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
varietal choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

flame weeding/ precision inter or intra-row hoes/electrical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
hot water or foam	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
robotic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
microwave	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
bio-herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
laser	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
allelopathy	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
targeted herbicide application (e.g. see and spray)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

Key for selection options

Main disadvantage

- 1) No significant disadvantages
- 2) time-consuming
- 3) complicated
- 4) expensive
- 5) Low efficacy
- 6) harmful to the environment and human
- 7) high carbon footprint
- 8) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)
- 9) Customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)

Current weed control problems / farmers (2)

8. What is your opinion on the following statements relating to weed control methods currently used on your farm?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1) no significant disadvantages	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) time-consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) complicated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) low efficacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6) harmful to the environment and human	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7) high carbon footprint	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9) customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Current weed control problems- farmers (3)

9. What specific weed types are not addressed by your current weed control methods? (Multiple choices available)

- Annual grass weeds
- Annual broad-leaved weeds
- Perennial grasses
- Perennial broad leaved weeds
- Other

9.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

Current weed control problems- farmers (4)

10. What is your opinion on the effects of herbicides on humans and the environment?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1) Long-term use of the same herbicide in the same field can cause weeds to develop resistance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) Herbicides and residues can accumulate in environment and have negative effects on organisms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) Herbicides or their residues can enter the human body through food	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) Herbicides contribute to the degradation of biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) Certain herbicides or their residues have carcinogenic properties	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Alternative weed control methods /farmers

11. Are there weed control methods that you are aware of and interested in, but have never used (multiple options possible)? Please indicate methods that you are interested in and select or specify one barrier describing why you have not tried this approach.

	Select	Main barrier
mechanical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
camera guided inter- row or intra-row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
cultivations/cultural control (delayed drilling, rotations, cover crops, cultivar choice, high seed rates)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
mowing	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
weeding by hand	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
mulches (membranes, organic)/living mulches	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
varietal choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
flame weeding	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
precision inter or intra- row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
electrical /hot water or foam	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
robotic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
microwave	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
bio-herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
laser	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
allelopathy	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
targeted herbicide application (e.g. see and spray)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
other method	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select

11.a. If 'other method' is selected, please specify in the box below

Key for selection options

Main disadvantage

- 10) No significant disadvantages
- 11) time-consuming
- 12) complicated
- 13) expensive
- 14) Low efficacy
- 15) harmful to the environment and human
- 16) high carbon footprint
- 17) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)
- 18) Customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)

Alternative weed control methods / farmers (2)

Are there weed control methods that you have tried in the past, that you are no longer using?

Please indicate methods that you have used and select or specify one main disadvantage describing why you no longer use this approach.

12.	Used	Main disadvantage	Why no longer use it
mechanical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
camera guided inter- row or intra- row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultivations	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultural control (delayed drilling, rotations, cover crops, cultivar choice, high seed rates)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mowing	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
weeding by hand	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mulches (membranes, organic)/living mulches	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
varietal choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
flame weeding	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
precision inter or intra-row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
electrical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
hot water or foam	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

robotic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
microwave	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
bio- herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
laser	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
allelopathy	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
targeted herbicide application (e.g. see and spray)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

12.a. If 'other method' is selected, please specify in the box below

Key for selection options

Main disadvantage

- 1) No significant disadvantages
- 2) time-consuming
- 3) complicated
- 4) expensive
- 5) Low efficacy
- 6) harmful to the environment and human
- 7) high carbon footprint
- 8) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)
- 9) Customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)

Alternative weed control methods / farmers (4)

13. How far do you agree with the following statements describing why farmers do not increase their use of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
There is a lack of information available about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
No skilled advisors available	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alternative weed control methods have low efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not have access to the required equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have heard negative reviews about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There are no opportunities to test alternative weed control method(s) before investing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The solutions are too expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulations do not allow the use of the particular method	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The method is time consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Negative effect on biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not know anyone that uses them	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other reason	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13.a. If you selected 'other reason', please specify.

Alternative weed control method / farmers (5)

14. In your opinion, how useful would the following scenarios be in order to increase the uptake of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Not useful	Slightly useful	Somewhat useful	Very useful	Extremely useful
Increased availability of information (Internet, newspapers, leaflets, booklets, Youtube, podcasts, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Consultations with a specialist or experienced user	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Recommendations from other farmers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Grants for the purchase of equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Demonstration events of the methods of interest	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Trials of alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Change of public opinion in favor of "greener" weed control methods (including food consumption habits)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Customer demands of reduced herbicide input	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Grants to establish trials to evaluate the effectiveness	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Introduction of stricter herbicide usage regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Other circumstances

14.a. If 'other' selected, please specify other circumstances that would promote the use of alternative weed control methods.

Alternative methods of weed control/ non-farmers

21. How far do you agree with the following statements describing why farmers do not increase their use of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	N/A or don't know
There is a lack of information available about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
No skilled advisors available	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alternative weed control methods have low efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not have access to the required equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have heard negative reviews about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There are no opportunities to test alternative weed control method(s) before investing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The solutions are too expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulations do not allow the use of the particular method	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The method is time consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Negative effect on biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not know anyone that uses them	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other reason	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

21.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

Alternative weed control/ non-farmers (2)

22. In your opinion, how useful would the following scenarios be in order to increase the uptake of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Not useful	Slightly useful	Somewhat useful	Very useful	Extremely useful	N/A or don't know
Increased availability of information (Internet, newspapers, leaflets, booklets, YouTube, podcasts, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Consultations with a specialist or experienced user	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Recommendations from other farmers	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Grants for the purchase of equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Demonstration events of the methods of interest	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Trials of alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Change of public opinion in favor of "greener" weed control methods (including food consumption habits)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Customer demands of reduced herbicide input	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Grants to establish trials to evaluate the effectiveness	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Introduction of stricter herbicide usage regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Other circumstances	<input type="checkbox"/>					

22.a. If 'other' selected, please specify other circumstances that would promote the use of alternative weed control methods

5. General questions

23. What is your age group?

- 20 or under
- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- 61 or over

24. What is the highest level of education you have attained

- Vocational qualification (Including BTEC, NVQ, OCR)
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- PhD
- Other

24.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

25. Do you have a specialised education in the field of agriculture? (please tick all that apply)

- No
- Vocational qualification with specialisation in agriculture
- Higher education with specialisation in agriculture
- Continuous professional development courses (CPD) Other
- formal qualification

25.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

General questions (2)

26. How long have you been working in the field of agriculture?

- up to 5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-20 years
- over 20 years N/A
- or don't know

27. Where do you get the latest news in agriculture (for example, about legislative changes, state support, grant programs, etc.)? (please tick all that apply)

- Social media
- From friends, acquaintances and colleagues
- Newspapers and magazines
- TV
- Radio
- Internet
- Seminars and events
- Consultants and advisors
- Direct contact with governmental representatives
- industry representatives
- Other

27.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

28. Are you a member of any non-governmental agricultural related organisations?

- No
- Trade union Farmer
- cooperative
- Horizontal non-governmental organisation (farmer to farmer) Professional
- non-governmental organisation (e.g farming unions) Other
- Don't Know

